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CHILDREN’S LITERATURE

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The purpose of this article: *to understand the essence of children's literature, to get acquainted with didactics.*

Also understand the difference between adult and children's literature, realizing their basic concept.

Key words: *literature, concept “reading and children”, fundamental difference, psychology, fantasy of child, adults’ and children's reality.*

Children's literature is a type of literature specially designed for children under 16 years of age and carrying out the tasks of raising and educating children in the language of artistic images.

In addition, there is the concept of "reading for children", which also includes works originally intended by the authors for adults, such as the famous fairy tales of A.S. Pushkin, Charles Perrault, W. Hauff, H.C. Andersen, the Brothers Grimm, and see also "Robinson Crusoe" by Daniel Defoe, "Gulliver's Travel" by Jonathan Swift and many others, and for children they adapt and simplify the retelling of complex literature, such as the last mentioned examples. Children's books are the material embodiment of literary works for children.

Analysis

Before talking about children's literature or literature for children, you need to define the concept of childhood and the child. So, in medical law and philosophy a child is considered as a person under 18 years of age. In psychology, according to some sources - up to 12 years, according to others - up to 16-17 years. In pedagogy in Russia - up to 12 years old. Margaret Mead spoke about children as a sub-ethnos in her work *Culture and the World of Childhood*.

L.S. Vygotsky devotes one of his works to the study of the fantasy of a child and adolescent (creative activity based on the combining ability of the human brain), where

he draws specific distinctions between them and adults.

Imagination depends on experience, and since the interests of a child and an adult are different, imagination works differently. In his opinion, a child's imagination is poorer than that of an adult, relations with reality are not so complex and diverse, but at the same time, a child or adolescent is more inclined to trust the products of his imagination.

A clear difference between the imagination of a child and an adult, and hence the perception of the world around, can further illustrate the need to separate literature for children and adults, where the former will construct images in the imagination differently.

The research was continued by the St. Petersburg Institute of Art Criticism. The child, as stated in these works, has a special picture of the world, a special perception of it, and folklore serves to convey such a picture of the world and to preserve it. It seems that the same can be said about children's literature.

One of the reasons for highlighting children's literature was its special connection with folklore, because the concept of children's folklore is generally accepted. In lyric poetry, as well as in many prose genres (school stories, "scary" stories) of children's literature, such a connection can be traced especially.

C.M. Leuter found that children's literature and folklore have common psycho-socio-cultural origins, which cannot be said about “adult” literature [Loiter 2002].

Examples of this can be found not only among folklorist writers (O.I Kapitsa, I.V Karnaukhova, T. Mavrina, etc.), but also in K.Chukovsky, who directly spoke about his appeals to folklore.

A real event for folklore studies was the large volume compiled by A.F. Belousov and owned by many authors - the anthology “Russian School Folklore”, in which school culture appeared broadly and multifaceted [Belousov 1998].¹

In science, there are many points of view on the issue of defining the concept of "children's folklore". So, for example, V.P. Anikin refers to children's folklore as "the creativity of adults for children, the creativity of adults, which eventually became children's, and children's creativity in the proper sense of the word".²

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Mythological genesis, poetic figurativeness (frequency of personifications, acoustic images), pronominal poetics, dialogism, rhythmic organization and intonational structure

- the basic principles of the poetics of children's verse - also go back to children's folklore [Leuter 2002, p. 274].

Like poetry for children, children's folklore has a playful character. Both in children's literature and in children's folklore there is a poeticization of the ordinary, fabulous transformations and similes, words are perceived as "an immense area of historical memory" [Leuter 2002, p. 40].

Several studies are connected with the clarification of the connection between the author's fairy tale and the folk tale [Leonova 1982; Ovchinnikova 2003].

According to Ovchinnikova, there is a difference between fairy tales for children and adults. It is expressed in the greater complexity of the artistic world in the literature not for children, the desire of the authors to reflect their “thinking” about the issues of time [Ovchinnikova 2003, p. 352]. The author's position here is multifaceted. To express it, the author uses different stylistic devices. Children's fairy tales are primarily characterized by didacticism as "lessons of traditional fairytales in a fascinating form" [Ovchinnikova 2003, p. 77].³

In addition to didacticism, thematic features of children's literature are also distinguished in the scientific tradition. I.G. Mineralova managed to generalize this circle of topics. Mineralova. According to her, children's literature seeks to show “what is and who is a child, what is his microcosm, what is his macrocosm, i.e. everything surrounding him” [Mineralova 2002, p. eighteen]. Indeed, the place of action in the

stories, one way or another subtitled “for children”, is not factories, offices or surgical departments, but a school (V. Golyavkin, V. Dragunsky, N. Nosov, M. Druzhinina), an apartment (O. Kurguzov, G. Oster), the countryside (“Uncle Fyodor, a dog and a cat”), a street (K. Dragunskaya, Yu. Moritz) and other topics that are within the child’s usual picture of the world.

Turning to the subject-object organization of the text, it is worth noting that the heroes of works for children often also become the children themselves. In the center of the plot of the most popular stories for children are "Vitya Maleev at school and at home", "The Adventures of Petrov and Vasechkin", "The Wizard of the Emerald City", "Deniska's stories", stories by K. Dragunskaya, O. Kurguzov,

M. Moskvina, E. Rakitina and many other children's writers, there is a character who is still in school, lives with his parents, brothers and sisters. But does it not turn out then that the novels “The Goldfinch” by D. Tart, “Lord of the Flies” by W. Golding, the story “Dandelion Wine” by R. Bradbury are children's literature?”⁴

It is impossible not to notice that literature for children shows a special content at all levels of text organization, which motivates us to look at the concept of children's

literature as a certain discursive formation that involves "a system of instances of the subject, object and addressee of discourse, which determines the parameters of communicative behavior (production and perception of texts) corresponding to the historically current state of public consciousness (sociocultural mentality)" [Tyupa 2008, p. 61]. In this case, in children's discourse, the addressee is the child, the object is the world familiar to the child, and the subject is the static image of the hero-child.

Thus, highlighting the fundamental differences between adult and children's literature raises many questions. The very category of the addressee, which is defined by the author in the title or subtitle or by the publisher in the label, does not

single out all the works that can be read and understood by children. In other cases, the addressee can only be assumed, and therefore it is difficult to consider him as the only true criterion. Moreover, the psychologically early development of the child, the complication of literary practices and, as a result, the migration of texts of adult literature in the past into the category of children's reading completely shifts the boundary between the adult and children's audience.

As a result of this study, it should be recognized that only with a combination of several criteria can those works be singled out that can now or in the future be addressed to the child. First of all, they are united by a common theme. Most often, a work for children is about children or small animals, in a sense, the same children.

Didacticism, which is often taken as a basis, is by no means characteristic of all works, as is clearly evidenced by absurd or playful poetry.

Topeka is also limited by the children's picture of the world, simplified, but illustrative, and time, despite the plot full of adventures and other events, stops and does not allow the characters to change externally and internally.

In most cases, the hero of children's literature is not yet a "ready-made" image, which can be expressed visually (when depicting size) or by naming age. The hero is static, but the world around him can change (including under his influence) and surprise him and the reader. Often the hero himself is the subject of speech, which indicates a pronounced, often the only, point of view. The chronotope, the type of the hero and the point of view may indicate some stylistic simplicity of the texts.

Thanks to the combination of these features at the level of poetics and themes, the work will resonate with the child and will be interesting to him. This will not mean that such a work is not available to an adult. Children's literature is a part of literature in general, and the above criteria will not narrow, but only expand the number of addressees.

The addressing of children's literature can thus be called double, and this will also

be its difference from literature in general, which presupposes one addressee - an adult. Despite the gradual development of ideas about children's literature, it is still necessary to describe the level of didacticism in modern children's literature, the set of dominant means of expression, to specify the features of the chronotope and points of view.

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